

Session H: Késia Decoté

Session Format	Presentation
Date	June 18, 2024 14:15 → 14:45
Room	Eikenes-salen
Chair	Wolfgang Schmid
Feedback 1	Heloise Baldelli

∨ 2 more properties

music as an invitation: processes of co-creation of an online piano concert

Keywords: music performance; piano performance; digital concert; co-creation; liveness; audience participation

"We" is the result of an "I" that opened up (that opened up to what she is not), that expanded, placed herself outside, expanded herself" (Marielle Macé, "Our cabins").

The project "music as an invitation", in its first year, invited women – musicians and non-musicians – to meet in online workshops to create an online concert collaboratively. Fourteen participants from different countries who joined the project.

The online workshops featured dynamics of conversations and sharing of ideas. Drawing from a Participatory Action Research approach, the participants were given total decision power to the development of the creative process, which then included individual creative explorations, dialogues, and collaborations. The final online concert was released on YouTube in April 2024*.

music as an invitation (year 1: 2023-2024)

This video is a collaborative work by Gloria Firmino Igara Cabral Katrin Hattenhauer Késia Decoté Laura Concheso Martínez Luciana Noda Luciana

<https://youtu.be/-zCYo5FRr8I?si=o89tO9bVrak53za8>

As the creative process unraveled, changes were taking place within the participants (and the group, as well): professional musicians now felt encouraged to express themselves creatively through other media, amateur pianists unlocked traumas and felt inspired to improvise for the first time, shy participants felt at home to share about themselves and inspire group explorations.

This presentation gives a glimpse of the unfolding of the story of this process of co-creation, where the "we" embraced the "I", who in return became "we" again.

This presentation aims to offer a view of the artistic work - which is the essence of this research - while presenting a contextualisation and commentary for an artistic-research peer audience. To this, a video essay format was chosen, which combines both elements so as to simultaneously allow an artistic and a scholarly reflective experience.

Artistic/academic references

- AUSLANDER, P. 2008 "Live and Technologically Mediated Performance", *The Cambridge Companion to Performance Studies*, T.C. Davis, ed., Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- CHEVALIER, J. M. & D. J. Buckles. 2019. *Participatory Action Research: theory and methods for engaged inquiry*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- TOELLE, J., & Sloboda, J. A. 2021. The *audience as artist?* The audience's experience of participatory music. *Musicae Scientiae*, 25(1), 67–91.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1029864919844804>
- MACÉ, Marielle, Isadora Bonfim Nuto, and Marcelo Jacques de Moraes. 2023. *Nossas Cabanas Lugares de Luta, Ideias Para a Vida Em Comum*. Rio de Janeiro: Bazar Do Tempo.
- ONO, Yoko. (1960/2019). Add Color (*Refugee Boat*). Participatory artistic installation. Video documentation at <https://youtu.be/gkm1eCaEXRs?si=SQV2wxJ7k06mX4bH> (Accessed 13 May 2024).

Format of presentation: video essay

music as an invitation: processes of co-creation on an online piano concert (presentation)

music as an invitation: processes of co-creation of an online piano concert

Length of presentation: 35 minutes

About Késia

Késia Decoté is a Brazilian pianist specialising in contemporary music and in interdisciplinary practices. Késia is interested in exploring innovative ways to present piano music, looking for creating unique and deeply immersive artistic experiences for her audience.

Késia holds a PhD in Arts & Music and MA (Distinction) from Oxford Brookes University, Masters Degree and Undergraduate (Cum laude) in Piano from the federal university of Rio de Janeiro.

Késia is a Marie Curie postdoctoral fellow at the University of Bergen developing a research project on new forms of participation of women and girls in classical music performances.

Késia Decoté. Photo © Phil Barnes